

ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ БИЗНЕС-ПРОЦЕССОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНЫХ КОМПАНИЯХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И АВТОМАТИЗАЦИИ

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OPTIMIZATION OF BUSINESS PROCESSES IN CONSTRUCTION COMPANIES USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND AUTOMATION

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена исследованию оптимизации бизнес-процессов в строительных компаниях через внедрение цифровых технологий и автоматизации. Рассматриваются ключевые инструменты, такие как технологии Building Information Modeling, интернет вещей, искусственный интеллект и системы управления проектами, которые способствуют улучшению качества проектирования, повышению эффективности и сокращению времени выполнения строительных работ. Охарактеризованы преимущества, такие как снижение затрат, повышение точности расчетов и улучшение взаимодействия между участниками процесса. Также акцентируется внимание на вызовах, таких как высокая стоимость внедрения технологий, недостаток квалифицированных кадров и сложности интеграции новых решений с существующими системами. Статья подчеркивает важность стратегического подхода к цифровизации для преодоления этих препятствий.

ABSTRACT

The article examines the optimization of business processes in construction companies through the implementation of digital technologies and automation. Key tools such as Building Information Modeling, Internet of Things, artificial intelligence, and project management systems are discussed, highlighting their role in improving design quality, increasing efficiency, and reducing construction time. The advantages, including cost reduction, improved calculation accuracy, and enhanced interaction among project participants, are explored. Challenges such as high implementation costs, a lack of qualified personnel, and difficulties in integrating new solutions with existing systems are also addressed. The article emphasizes the importance of a strategic approach to digitalization to overcome these obstacles.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, автоматизация, Building Information Modeling, Internet of Things, управление проектами, строительство.

Keywords: digitalization, automation, Building Information Modeling, Internet of Things, project management, construction.

Introduction

The structure of the modern construction company becomes increasingly important because of business process development for increasing efficiency and competitiveness. Traditional project management methods, based on paper documentation and manual calculations, cannot provide the required flexibility and efficiency. Digitalization and automation of work represent promising strategic solutions to this challenge.

In contrast, new and more enhanced digital technologies are being gradually introduced in the construction industry that are aimed at enhancing design quality and accuracy, while easing the handling of project management. Enhanced realities through Building Information Modeling (BIM) allow for accurate designs at faster completion times, which contributes to reduction in overall costs through optimizations within internal organizational processes, plus transparency to all parties concerned. This in return enhances member cooperation within a team, resulting in successful projects.

The article discusses the advantages created for construction firms by digital technologies and automation of processes in order to enhance their business. It

emphasizes the main advantages of such kind of novelties and points out potential obstacles which may appear for construction companies in the process of adoption.

Main part. Digitalization and automation in construction

The main transformational elements in the construction industry are digitalization and automation, both of which contribute significantly to increasing efficiency and competitiveness for building companies. Digital technologies enhance the quality of the design and optimize workflow at all stages of construction, from planning and design to the management of buildings and structures in operation. Key enablers involve project management platforms, BIM, artificial intelligence (AI), and construction site management and controlling tools. It incorporates BIM in developing a 3D model with information on the structure that will have details on material, scheduling, and cost involved. BIM enhances coordination by reducing errors and hence smoothing budgeting and scheduling. BIM minimizes material and resource costs by fast-tracking de-

sign and construction workflow and on-site modifications. BIM also saves on costs and helps large projects not to exceed the budgets allocated for it.

Efficiency in the line of construction involves automating most processes related to the control of equipment, flow and logistics, and managing how functions are performed. Internet of Things (IoT) sensors installed at a building site, for example, observe the real-time condition of equipment so that chances for breakdown can be reduced, adding to the general output of labor. With the development and implementation of such technologies, construction firms will manage to simplify the operations and minimize downtime in order to exploit resources much more appropriately to achieve great results from their projects [1].

Digitalization and automation in the construction industry have huge positive impacts on productivity, cost efficiency, quality, and project timelines. These technologies also enable designers, contractors, and clients to be more collaborative due to transparency and control in all stages of construction. A very straightforward example is the **Autodesk Tandem** platform, which develops the design quickly and reduces possible errors during construction [2].

Limitations and challenges of digital technology implementation

The introduction of digital technologies and automation in construction companies is associated with a number of significant challenges and limitations that can slow down or even prevent the effective use of these solutions (table 1).

Table 1.

Main blockers that slow down the introduction of new technologies [3]

Blocker	Description	Impact on implementation	Possible solutions
High initial costs	Significant financial investment required for new technologies, including hardware, software, and training.	Delayed adoption or avoidance of new technologies.	Subsidies, phased implementation, government grants, or leasing options.
Lack of skilled workforce	Insufficient expertise among staff to operate and maintain digital tools effectively.	Inefficient use or underutilization of technologies.	Training programs, partnerships with educational institutions.
Resistance to change	Employees and management may resist adopting new methods due to fear of disruption or loss of control.	Slower transition to new systems, reduced efficiency.	Change management strategies, employee involvement, and demonstration of technology benefits.
Fragmentation of the industry	Construction involves multiple stakeholders, making integration of technologies across teams challenging.	Reduced collaboration and inconsistent adoption.	Standardized tools, collaborative platforms, and stakeholder alignment on project goals.
Outdated infrastructure	Existing systems and equipment may not support seamless adoption of advanced digital technologies.	High costs for upgrades or operational inefficiencies.	Gradual upgrades, retrofitting old systems, and integrating new tools/

On a general note, serious hurdles are the high implementation cost with regard to new technologies by way of equipment, personnel training, and system integration. For many small and medium enterprises, such costs already represent a significant burden and thus often turn out to be a bottleneck in the transition toward a digital solution. Research has shown that on average, investments in the digitalization of construction companies can make up 5 to 10% of the cost of the overall project, which is a lot at the initial stage despite all the long-term benefits [4].

It involves serious issues: a shortage of competent professionals. Only highly skilled specialists can provide the proper adaptation of such solutions to company needs and implement these technologies like BIM or project management systems effectively. Without these

professionals, it causes a failure in technology implementation that may rise to increased costs related to personnel training [5]. In such conditions, complete abandonment of digital solutions takes place or, worse, goes to worse solutions.

Technical complexity integrating new technologies with existing systems is another challenge. Construction companies use different software solutions at different stages of their work, and integrating new tools may require time for adaptation and testing. Compatibility issues can slow down project execution and increase operational costs due to the need for additional resources to resolve issues.

In addition, resistance to change from employees and management is also a common barrier to successful digitalization (fig. 1).

Fig.1. Responses to perceived improvements driven by digital processes and practices in 2023 [6]

Besides that, workers may feel the work automation is suspected and be less motivated to cognize and use new technologies. After all, successful digitalization, besides technical equipment, presupposes a change in corporate culture, which is an extremely long and labor-consuming process.

In general, automation of business processes in construction provides an opportunity for enhancing the effectiveness of works in all stages of the project, from the plan development stage up to delivering the facility. Conducting projects with the participation of the systems for the management of a project and resource control lowers the chances of mistakes, thereby improving the accuracy of performing the calculations and reporting. Logistics optimization: An automated system reduces material and equipment delivery time by considering a lot of factors such as weather, transport availability, and traffic congestion that make deliveries slower. For example, logistics information is integrated in an effort to optimize the transport flux and reduce delivery time for materials that finally will reduce costs in **Procure Technologies** [7].

Automation of resource management allows companies to track material consumption, manage labor costs, and analyze productivity. This data helps to more effectively reallocate resources and optimize work processes, reducing costs and improving the quality of work. In the area of quality management, automation helps to monitor compliance with building codes and standards, identify nonconformities in due time, and eliminate them, which reduces the number of reworks and increases customer satisfaction [8].

Prospects for optimizing business processes in construction companies

The future of the construction industry strongly relates to the adoption of digital technologies and automation, which can transform business operations and make them more effective. As was mentioned earlier, one of the key trends is the adoption of AI in construction operations. In the future, AI technologies can form the foundation for autonomous construction site management and logistics process optimization.

A broader use of BIM across all stages of a building's life cycle, i.e., design, build, and operate, will reduce expenses, minimize errors, and make interactions between project stakeholders more open. In parallel with this, equipping building construction sites with robots and 3D printers opens up horizons for accelerating project completion and reducing labor dependency.

The widespread use of IoT will enable real-time monitoring of construction equipment, materials, and structures, leading to greater security and more efficient project management. In addition, energy efficiency and sustainability will be integrated into construction projects. Digital technology will enable the development of sustainable structures with high energy-saving performance, while automation will decrease carbon emissions.

Cloud computing and big data analytics may speed up decision-making, enhance the accuracy of projections, and bring all parties to the construction process closer to collaboration. One of the major trends of the future might be the development of digital twins, whereby virtual representations of buildings and infrastructure can be created to reproduce various conditions of operation, detect flaws, and predict alterations.

The future of the construction sector is thus in the realm of digital technology and robotics. These emerg-

ing trends not only enhance the competitiveness of construction companies but also render them sustainable in terms of modern standards and efficient in practice.

Conclusion

Digitalization and automation of business processes are becoming not only a necessity but also an important factor that guarantees competitiveness in the modern market. Advanced technologies like BIM, IoT, and project management systems integrated into all stages of construction-from design to operation-significantly raise efficiency. These solutions reduce costs, improve the quality of work, and speed up the completion time of projects.

Simultaneously, it is a path burdened with several challenges: high investment cost, shortage of qualified specialists, technical difficulties in new and old system integration, resistance to change from employees, etc. Construction companies can be successful in digitalization only if the above-mentioned obstacles may be bypassed by taking strategic plans and governmental supports and making an investment into personnel training.

Despite all difficulties at the initial stage, in the long-term outlook, there is indeed a gain from digital technologies implementation in construction: increase in productivity, cost reduction, and improvement of work quality are the key factors that provide growth and successful adaptation of companies in conditions of modern economic competition.

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